

A Study of the Complex Compounds of *N*-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part III. *o*-Aminobenzenesulphonyl Glycine

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o-Aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (RH₂) forms complexes with Cu, Ag, Zn, and Cd, but a pure product could not be isolated with mercury. The green copper-complex and colorless Zn- and Cd-complexes are of the general formula Mⁿ (RH)(OH) H₂O (where Mⁿ=Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II)). Silver compounds isolated are of the types AgRH₂·2H₂O and Ag₃R(RH). The former one is a weak monobasic acid and its pK has been determined by potentiometric titration as 3.80. The green crystalline copper compound on dehydration loses 1.5 molecules of water to furnish a green solid, RHCu. O. CuRH.

The use of sulphonamide group (-SO₂-NH₂) in complexing agents was first introduced by Billman *et al*.¹ Later, Ghosh and Majumder^{2,3} prepared *N*-benzenesulphonyl glycine and its nitroderivatives and studied their dissociation constants as well as the complexes formed with a number of cations.

The interesting results obtained in this field led the present authors to prepare the *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine and study its properties and reactions with different metal cations. With copper, zinc, and cadmium, the complex was of the formula M (RH) (OH) H₂O, where M = Cu (II), Zn (II), Cd (II), and RH₂ =

With silver, two compounds were obtained, the simple one, Ag (RH) RH₂·2H₂O and a more complex one, Ag₃R(RH). Mercury compounds could not be isolated in a pure state.

The potentiometric titration of AgRH(RH₂)·2H₂O shows that the compound is a weak monobasic acid and on further addition of alkali, condensation to a polynuclear complex, Ag₃R(RH), takes place.

The steps may be represented by the following equations:

1. *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 1942.
2. *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 845.
3. Communicated to this *Journal*.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine was prepared by reduction in the cold with alkaline $[\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2]^4$ of *o*-nitrobenzenesulphonyl glycine which was obtained by the interaction of glycine and *o*-nitrobenzenesulphonyl chloride in presence of alkali. The reagent, *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine was recrystallised from ethanol or hot water, m.p. 170° (Found: C, 41.81; H, 4.61; N, 12.18; Equiv. 230.5 Calc. C, 41.74; H, 4.35; N, 12.17%); Equiv. 230.) It is soluble in acetone, ethanol and hot water; sparingly soluble in cold water and insoluble in benzene, ether etc.

Complex Compounds with Metal Ions

(A) *Copper* (II).—Solution of the reagent in ethanol in a stoppered conical flask was mixed with an aqueous suspension of freshly prepared CuO in the ratio 1:1. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and heated on a steam bath till the CuO went into solution; the solution was deep green with bright green crystals visible at the bottom. It was filtered and the filtrate was left overnight when bright green crystals were formed. The crystals were collected, washed with ethanol and air-dried. $\mu_B = 1.86$ B.M. (Found: Cu, 19.16; N, 8.78 Cu (RH) (OH) H_2O requires Cu, 19.41; N, 8.55%).

On dehydration at 105° it lost in weight and the loss corresponded to 1.5 molecules of H_2O (Loss found, 7.91; calc. 8.24%). After dehydration was left a green insoluble powder possibly having the structure $\text{HR}_2\text{Cu}_2\text{O.Cu.RH}$, $\mu_B = 1.47$ B.M. (Found: Cu, 21.30; N, 9.47; Calc.: Cu, 21.13; N, 9.32%).

(B) *Zinc* (II).—The zinc complex was prepared and isolated in the same way as the preceding Cu compound. (Found: Zn, 19.81; N, 8.35. Calc. for Zn (RH) (OH) H_2O Zn, 19.85; N, 8.50%).

(C) *Cadmium* (II).—The solution of the reagent in hot water was treated with freshly prepared CdO in a stoppered conical flask in the ratio 1:1. The reagent was slightly in excess. The mixture was warmed on a steam bath when the Cd compound was precipitated; it was filtered and washed with ethanol to remove any excess reagent. (Found: Cd, 29.89; N, 7.83. Calc. for Cd (RH) (OH) H_2O . Cd, 29.86; N, 7.44%).

(D) *Silver*.—With silver, two compounds were obtained. In the first Ag to reagent ratio was 1:2 and in the second it was 3:2.

(a). To the solution of the reagent in hot water was added freshly precipitated Ag_2O ($\text{Ag}_2\text{O}:\text{RH}_2=1:4$) and shaken well for sometime on a water bath. The upper solution took a reddish tinge. It was filtered and the filtrate kept overnight, when fine light orange crystals appeared. It was filtered and washed with ethanol to remove the excess reagent. In the compound Ag:N was 1:4. [Found: Ag, 17.92; N, 9.20. Ag (RH) $\text{RH}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ag, 17.89; N, 9.29%]. The compound is sparingly soluble in water. The solution on treatment with alkali precipitates the second compound Ag_3R (RH) at pH=5 to 6.

(b). A solution of the reagent in hot water was treated with AgNO_3 solution and pH was adjusted at 5. A precipitate appeared. It dissolved in higher or lower pH. It was

filtered, washed with ethanol and air-dried. The colour of the compound was white with brownish tinge. Ag:N ratio was found to be 3:4 [Found: Ag, 41.46; N, 7.20. Ag₃(RH)R requires Ag, 41.46; N, 7.17%]. This compound when heated with excess reagent formed a solution with reddish tinge and on subsequent filtration and crystallisation furnished the compound Ag(RH)RH₂, 2H₂O.

Potentiometric Titration of the Silver Compound Ag(RH)RH₂, 2H₂O

A standard solution of alkali was made by dissolving A.R. quality KOH in 0.1M KNO₃ solution. The solution was standardised with hydrazine sulphate.

A standard solution of Ag(RH)(RH₂), 2H₂O was made by dissolving weighed amount of the pure dry crystals in 0.1M KNO₃ solution.

The solution of the silver compound (2.35 × 10⁻³M, 200 ml) was titrated with the standard alkali solution (0.265M). The resulting pH values were noted and the corresponding $\bar{\eta}_H$ values were calculated (Table I). *pK* for the complex acid being equal to *pH* when $\bar{\eta}_H = \frac{1}{2}$, was found to be 3.80 ($\mu = 0.1$) at 25°. After titration, the precipitate formed at *pH* ≈ 5 to 6 was collected and analysed. (Found: Ag, 41.72. Ag₃(RH)R requires Ag, 41.46%)

TABLE I

Alkali added	<i>pH</i>	ΔpH	$\bar{\eta}_H$	Alkali added	<i>pH</i>	ΔpH	$\bar{\eta}_H$
		Δ^v				Δ^v	
0.00ml	3.47	—	0.86	1.70ml	4.77	1.85	0.04
0.10	3.51	0.40	0.81	1.80	4.95	0.90	—
0.30	3.60	0.45	0.73	2.10	5.03	0.40	..
0.55	3.71	0.44	0.61	2.30	5.21	0.80	..
0.80	3.82	0.44	0.48	2.55	5.57	1.44	..
1.00	3.94	0.60	0.39	2.70	6.12	3.67	..
1.20	4.09	0.75	0.29	3.00	9.77	12.17	..
1.50	4.40	1.03	0.14	3.60	10.53	1.52	..

FIG. 1. Volume of alkali added (ml) →

From the curve obtained by plotting $\Delta pH/\Delta v$ vs. the volume of alkali added (Fig 1), it is evident that there are three breaks corresponding to 1.70, 2.45 and 3.00 ml of alkali added representing the three steps of the reaction. [Found: The ratios of Ag-compound to alkali—representing these steps of reaction, 1 : 0.96; 1 : 1.38; 1 : 1.66. Calc. 1:1; 1:1.33; 1:1.67]. The discrepancies from the anticipated values are due to overlapping of the first and the second steps, and the second and the third steps of the reaction.

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Received July 26, 1965.